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1 MS2.4 First iteration of FAIR implementation framework

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Lead Author (Org)	Joy Davidson (DCC-UEDIN)
Contributing Author(s) (Org)	Sara Pittonet (Trust-IT), Lisa de Leeuw (DANS), Vasso Kalaitzi (DANS)
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Dissemination Level

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2 Versioning and contribution history

Version	Date	Author	Notes
0.1	08.08.2023	Joy Davidson (DCC-UEDIN)	TOC and V0.1
0.2	10.08.2023	Vasso Kalaitzi and Lisa de Leeuw (DANS)	review of v0.1
1.0	28.08.2023	Joy Davidson (DCC-UEDIN)	updated version published to FAIR-IMPACT Zenodo community

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TERMINOLOGY

Terminology/Acronym	Description
EC	European Commission
FIF	FAIR Implementation Framework

4 Introduction

FAIR-IMPACT aims to support the implementation phase of the European Open Science Cloud by helping a wide range of stakeholders, and especially Research Performing Organisations (RPOs), repositories, data and metadata service providers (including persistent identifier services and semantic services) and national level initiatives to take up and further develop FAIR-enabling practices, tools and services. To this end, FAIR-IMPACT carried out a targeted landscape analysis to identify viable tools, methods and solutions that have been produced by the recent H2020 INFRAEOSC FAIR-related projects and that are currently available to support FAIR Implementation in a practical sense. The resulting FAIR Implementation Framework (FIF) catalogue of resources is accessible via the FAIR-IMPACT website to enable others to find, assess and adopt them: <https://fair-impact.eu/ImplementationFramework-inputform>.

The FAIR Implementation Framework itself consists of seven components (including the catalogue of resources) and is intended to help our key stakeholders to consider the bigger picture when it comes to enabling FAIR. The FIF will be instrumental for framing the delivery of our Route 1 dedicated guidance and one-to-one support programme to RPOs, repositories and data service providers, and national level initiatives¹, but the framework will also be openly available to support adoption by a wider range of stakeholders across Europe and globally.

The framework's catalogue of resources will be updated periodically to ensure that emerging approaches, tools and resources such as those resulting from ongoing related projects and initiatives are included.

¹ <https://fair-impact.eu/fair-impact-open-calls-support>

5 Description of the Milestone

The FAIR Implementation Framework comprises seven elements and the first iteration of the was presented in D2.1 Targeted landscape analysis report² and made available for public comment on 31 January 2023. The framework suggests a workflow that stakeholders wishing to become more FAIR-enabling might follow to ensure they have a firm understanding of where they are now and where they want to be.

First, stakeholders are urged to consider their drivers for becoming more FAIR-enabling and then to self-assess their current capabilities for providing FAIR-enabling services and support and to identify areas where progress is required.

Based on the self-assessment, stakeholders then move on to develop a practical action plan for realising their FAIR-enabling objectives. Engagement with additional actors required to implement the plan as well as any end users expected to adopt new practices is critical to successful implementation. To this end, the FIF urges stakeholders to consider how they will work with different actors to carry out implementation and to develop an engagement strategy targeted to end users.

Based on the outcomes of their self-assessment and action plan, stakeholders should now look for existing tools/approaches/solutions that will support their FAIR-enabling objectives. The FIF catalogue of resources aims to help stakeholders to more easily find and reuse existing FAIR-enabling resources.

During the implementation stage, stakeholders should consider how they will measure success/failure and monitor uptake over the longer term. Finally, the FIF suggests that

² Davidson, Joy, Pittonet, Sara, Boerman, Sandra, Brinkman, Loek, Jonquet, Clement, Kalaitzi, Vasso, Kechagioglou, Xenii, L'Hours, Herve, Marjamaa-Mankinen, Liisa, Mathers, Benjamin, Meneses, Rita, Nordling, Josefine, O'Connor, Ryan, & Gonzalez-Beltran, Alejandra. (2023). D2.1 Targeted landscape analysis report (V1.0 DRAFT NOT YET APPROVED BY THE EUROPEAN COMMISSION). Zenodo.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7581670>

stakeholders share their experiences to help others by publishing their experience as a FAIR Implementation Story.

As shown above, the catalogue of current tools/methods/approaches is a key component of the FAIR Implementation Framework. Desk research was carried out to identify a set of 60+ candidate resources for inclusion in the first iteration of the FIF. These were presented in the annex of D2.1 Targeted landscape analysis report. During March/April 2023, each of the candidate resources were reviewed by three members of the FAIR Implementation Team³ and a consensus meeting was held to review the outcomes and agree on the list of resources to be included in the first iteration of the FIF catalogue.

Between February and May 2023, DCC and Trust-IT worked to create a prototype of the browsable version of the FIF catalogue. During the work to develop the prototype of the FIF catalogue of resources, FAIR-IMPACT was careful to align our descriptive fields with the metadata fields employed by the EOSC portal.

5.1 Role of the milestone report

This milestone report provides evidence that the first iteration of the FAIR Implementation Framework and the FIF catalogue of resources was published as planned by 31 May 2023.

5.2 Means of verification

Trust-IT has created a dedicated web presence for the FAIR Implementation Framework and the FIF catalogue of resources⁴.

Figure 1. FAIR Implementation Framework website

³ <https://fair-impact.eu/fair-implementation-team>

⁴ <https://fair-impact.eu/ImplementationFramework-inputform>

6 Next steps

Work will continue on the prototype FIF catalogue in summer/autumn 2023. An updated version of the catalogue will be released in November 2023. As work on the prototype continues, we will follow the advice emerging from our partners in WP4 on making semantic artefacts such as catalogues FAIR.